

Use Of Chat Generative Pre-Trained Transformer, Workload, And Social Media Management of Selected Private Schools in The City of Biñan, Laguna

Jade Allen R. Pilar

jadepilar1999@gmail.com

University of Perpetual Help System, Laguna-Philippines

Ernesto A. Serrano, Jr.

serrano.ernesto@uphsl.edu.ph

University of Perpetual Help System, Laguna-Philippines

ABSTRACT

The role of AI tools like ChatGPT in private school marketing emphasizes their effectiveness in generating engaging content, automating repetitive tasks, and assisting in enrollment marketing by influencing prospective families' school searches (Bernardi 2025). This study explores the adoption of ChatGPT, workload management, and social media strategies (Facebook, TikTok, Instagram) in selected private schools in Biñan, Laguna. It aims to assess the relationship between ChatGPT use, workload, and social media management. Using stratified random sampling, 49 marketing staff from eight private schools participated, with data collected via a validated questionnaire. Findings show a strong adoption of ChatGPT (mean = 3.49), a very high workload (mean = 3.61), and high social media use, especially Facebook (mean = 3.65) and TikTok (mean = 3.30). Significant correlations were found between ChatGPT adoption, workload, and social media management. An action plan was proposed to optimize ChatGPT use, improve workload management, and enhance social media strategies for better efficiency and engagement.

Keywords: *ChatGPT, AI, Workload Management, Social Media, Private Schools, Facebook, TikTok, Instagram, Marketing Strategies.*

INTRODUCTION

Chat-Generative Pre-Trained Transformers (ChatGPT) and other artificial intelligence (AI) technologies are revolutionizing sectors, including education. These AI tools automate chores, increase productivity, improve organization and communication, and replicate human thought processes (Piper, 2022). Especially in private school marketing, ChatGPT has evolved into a component of social media management. ChatGPT also helps with content production, scheduling, and web presence. These marketing efforts influenced how prospective families search for schools (Bernardi, 2025). Waddington (2023) stresses the need for educational institutions since AI-driven marketing affects audience involvement. Garcia and Santos (2023) also investigated how artificial intelligence may be used in digital marketing for Manila's

Received: 4 April 2025

Revised: 10 April 2025

Accepted: 27 April 2025

Copyright ♥ authors 2025

655

DOI: [HTTPS://DOI.ORG/10.5281/ZENODO.15345830](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15345830)

private schools to show how ChatGPT increases the school's exposure and involvement while lowering manual labor.

As artificial intelligence keeps being involved in digital marketing, its relevance in task management has become extremely important and is also growing more significant. Work intensification that many teachers and school administrators experience causes stress and burnout (Creagh, 2023). In private schools with limited resources, juggling marketing, administrative, and academic obligations can be especially difficult. Beech (2025) supports the theory that by automating administrative and marketing efforts, AI systems can increase production, therefore relieving the load on school staff members.

Magtalas (2024) examined the connection between teacher workload, burnout, and work performance, demonstrating that AI-supported automation can help manage stress and improve efficiency. Given these findings, the potential for AI to lessen the workload of teachers and administrative officers highlights the importance of exploring its role in workload management within private schools.

Managing social media accounts requires continuous content creation, strategic posting, and interaction with the audience that can be time-consuming and labor-intensive. Sonnenberg (2025) asserts that AI tools like ChatGPT can optimize content development, reducing staff workload while improving engagement strategies. Social media management is another critical aspect of modern educational marketing. Private schools rely on social media platforms to maintain their virtual presence, engage with the school community, and communicate their values effectively (Jacobson, 2020).

Automating processes such as content scheduling, performance tracking, and audience analysis, AI can streamline marketing operations and enhance digital outreach for schools (Beech, 2025). Additionally, Cortis and Davis (2021) highlight the role of social media management in monitoring and analyzing public sentiment, which shapes branding and engagement strategies.

However, despite extensive research on AI, no study has yet been conducted, particularly in the selected private schools in the City of Biñan, Laguna, which talks about Chat generative pre-trained transformer, workload, and social media management.

This study aimed to examine the challenges schools may face in integrating AI-driven marketing strategies. By identifying potential obstacles and offering practical recommendations, this research would help private schools optimize AI tools for marketing and workload management. Ultimately, the findings would contribute to the growing body of knowledge on AI-driven strategies in education, enabling schools to refine their marketing efforts and digital engagement initiatives. Through a focused analysis, this research would provide valuable insights into how AI tools assist in content creation, audience engagement, and campaign management.

METHODS

Received: 4 April 2025

Revised: 10 April 2025

Accepted: 27 April 2025

Copyright ♥ authors 2025

656

DOI: [HTTPS://DOI.ORG/10.5281/ZENODO.15345830](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15345830)

The researcher discusses the methodology in detail, focusing on the research design, participant selection, data collection process, and analysis. It utilized a descriptive-correlational research design, which is a method that both describes characteristics of a phenomenon and examines relationships between variables. The researcher aimed to explore how the use of ChatGPT influences workload and social media management within the context of private schools in Biñan, Laguna. By using this research design, the researcher could gather information about *what* (the impact of ChatGPT, workload, and social media management) and examine *how* or *why* these variables are related, without manipulating any variables.

The study focused specifically on marketing staff in selected private schools, as they are directly involved with managing social media platforms for their institutions and likely to be using ChatGPT to assist in these tasks. The schools included in the study were varied, encompassing institutions like Saint Michael's College, Trimex Colleges, University of Perpetual Help System Laguna, and others. A total of 49 participants were selected using a stratified sampling technique, ensuring that the sample was representative of the marketing personnel with knowledge of both social media management and ChatGPT usage. Stratified sampling helps ensure that key subgroups (in this case, marketing staff familiar with ChatGPT) are appropriately represented in the sample, which contributes to the generalizability and relevance of the findings.

The researcher crafted a self-made questionnaire as the primary tool for data collection, divided into three distinct sections that reflected the focus of the study. Part 1 assessed the adoption of ChatGPT, Part 2 examined the level of workload, and Part 3 focused on social media management. This instrument was designed to capture relevant data on how each of these areas impacts marketing staff's daily tasks and overall effectiveness.

Also, the validation and reliability of the questionnaire were key concerns in ensuring the quality of the data collected. The researcher sought expert advice and conducted face validation, which involved presenting the instrument to a panel of experts in research methodology, statistics, and the specific field of study. This allowed for revisions and refinements based on expert recommendations. The reliability of the instrument was then tested using Cronbach's Alpha, which measures the internal consistency of the items within each section. The high Cronbach's Alpha values (above 0.97) indicated that the items in each section were highly reliable, meaning the questionnaire consistently measured what it was intended to measure.

Regarding the data gathering procedure, the researcher followed a systematic process to ensure the integrity of the data. First, approvals were obtained from relevant authorities, including the dean of graduate studies and school administrators. This ensured that the research adhered to ethical standards and that participants were aware of their rights. The researcher distributed the surveys in person, allowing for direct interaction with the participants, providing clear instructions, and addressing any concerns. This approach facilitated greater participation and allowed the researcher to emphasize the voluntary nature of the study, ensuring that participants were willing and informed.

After the data was collected, it was systematically entered into a database or statistical software for analysis, ensuring data integrity and confidentiality. The data analysis itself employed two statistical tools. First, the weighted mean was used to assess the adoption of ChatGPT, the level of workload, and the effectiveness of social media management, providing an average measure for each variable based on the responses. Second, Pearson's r correlation was used to analyze the relationships between the three main variables of the study—ChatGPT adoption, workload, and social media management. Pearson's r is a measure of the strength and direction of the linear relationship between two continuous variables. By using this statistical method, the researcher was able to identify and measure the significance of the correlations between these variables, providing insights into how changes in one might impact the others

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The following tables and textual presentations provide a discussion of the adoption of Chat-Generative Pre-Trained Transformer, workload, and social media management of selected private schools in the City of Biñan, Laguna.

Table 1
The Adoption of Chat-Generative Pre-Trained Transformer of selected private schools in the City of Biñan, Laguna

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. ChatGPT has made managing the school's social media platforms efficient and time-saving.	3.53	Strongly Agree	6
2. Using ChatGPT has improved the consistency of content posted on the school's social media accounts.	3.63	Strongly Agree	1
3. ChatGPT helps create social media content quickly and efficiently.	3.59	Strongly Agree	2.5
4. The integration of ChatGPT has improved the effectiveness of the school's online marketing campaigns.	3.55	Strongly Agree	4.5
5. ChatGPT has contributed to increasing engagement with the school's target audience on social media.	3.43	Strongly Agree	7
6. ChatGPT's ability to automate responses has reduced the workload when handling routine inquiries.	3.33	Strongly Agree	9.5
7. ChatGPT helps in drafting in all social media posts for school events.	3.41	Strongly Agree	8

8. The use of ChatGPT has helped track to analyze social media performance, leading to more informed decision-making for future content.	3.33	Strongly Agree	9.5
9. ChatGPT has enhanced the ability to customize social media content to better connect with the school's audience.	3.59	Strongly Agree	2.5
10. The use of ChatGPT has made the overall management of the school's social media presence more organized.	3.55	Strongly Agree	4.5
Overall Weighted Mean	3.49	Strongly Agree	

The data presented in Table 1 reveals that the marketing staff from selected private schools in the City of Biñan, Laguna, "strongly agreed" on the adoption of ChatGPT, with an overall weighted mean of 3.49. ChatGPT has improved the consistency of content posted on the school's social media accounts, efficiently creates social media content, and enhances the ability to customize social media content to better connect with the school's audience. The highest-rated indicator, with a weighted mean of 3.63, was the improvement in the consistency of content posted. Other indicators that scored highly include the efficiency in creating social media content (3.59) and the ability to personalize content (3.59). The integration of ChatGPT also improved online marketing effectiveness (3.55) and organization (3.55).

The results of the study align with previous research, including Bernardi (2025) and Bose (2024), ChatGPT in private schools demonstrated its effectiveness in making content align with the institutional educational goal in improving social media engagement. Fawley (2024) showed a similar study on Artificial Intelligence (ChatGPT), igniting content ideas, planning, and maintaining an online presence supports the private schools in managing their digital platforms. Stated to Garcia and Santos (2023), in the context of private schools in Manila, ChatGPT improved the visibility and engagement of social media platforms while reducing the manual workload.

Table 2
The Level of Workload of the Respondents in Selected Private Schools in the City of Biñan, Laguna

Indicator	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. I find that my current workload in the marketing department is manageable.	3.61	Very High	5.5
2. I have the necessary resources to manage my workload in the marketing department.	3.63	Very High	3.5
3. I feel supported by school management in handling my workload.	3.59	Very High	7
4. I can efficiently meet deadlines without compromising the quality of my work.	3.55	Very High	9

5. I feel confident in my ability to handle my daily workload in the marketing department.	3.51	Very High	10
6. I receive adequate feedback from management on how to improve my efficiency handling my workload.	3.57	Very High	8
7. I have enough time to focus on my daily tasks and long-term marketing goals.	3.71	Very High	1
8. I feel that my workload allows me to engage in continuous professional development.	3.63	Very High	3.5
9. I find that there is a clear division of labor within our department.	3.61	Very High	5.5
10. I experience strong collaboration among team members that helps us manage the marketing workload.	3.67	Very High	2
Overall Weighted Mean	3.61	Very High	

Table 2 shows that the respondents from selected private schools in the City of Biñan, Laguna, reported a "very high" level of workload, with an average weighted mean of 3.61. The findings indicate that the workload enables respondents to focus on daily tasks, long-term marketing goals, foster strong team collaboration, and engage in professional development. The highest-rated indicator, with a weighted mean of 3.71, was the ability to focus on daily tasks and long-term goals, followed by strong collaboration (3.67). Other key indicators included having resources to manage the workload (3.63) and being able to engage in professional development (3.63).

The results align with studies by Bernardi (2025), Petrescu and Krishen (2023), and Kumar (2024), highlighting the importance of AI tools like ChatGPT in improving workplace dynamics. Bernardi (2025) shows that AI reduces cognitive load, allowing employees to focus on strategic tasks and long-term goals, boosting productivity. Petrescu and Krishen (2023) emphasize AI's role in enhancing collaboration by streamlining workflows and enabling employees to focus on complex tasks, improving team performance. Kumar (2024) underscores how AI fosters professional development, motivating employees to upskill and align with organizational goals. Overall, AI tools contribute to better task management, collaboration, and employee growth, driving both individual and organizational success.

Table 3
Composite Table of the Social Media Management Utilized by Selected Private Schools in the City of Biñan, Laguna

Indicator	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. Facebook	3.65	Strongly Agree	1
2. TikTok	3.30	Strongly Agree	2
3. Instagram	3.23	Agree	3
Overall Weighted Mean	3.39	Strongly Agree	

Table 3 reveals that the social media management strategies used by selected private schools in the City of Biñan, Laguna, were perceived as effective by marketing staff, with an

Received: 4 April 2025

Revised: 10 April 2025

Accepted: 27 April 2025

Copyright ♥ authors 2025

overall weighted mean of 3.39. Facebook ranked highest with a weighted mean of 3.65, followed by TikTok (3.30) and Instagram (3.23). These results indicate that social media management has effectively enhanced the schools' online visibility and presence.

The findings on social media management effectiveness in Biñan's private schools align with prior research. Facebook is the most influential platform for schools due to its broad reach and engagement versatility (Marques & Camacho, 2022). TikTok, with its short-form video content, boosts engagement with younger audiences (Almahallawi & Aljarallah, 2023). Instagram plays a key role in building brand identity, but it ranks lower in engagement (Tafesse, 2020). This study confirms Facebook's top rank, followed by TikTok and Instagram.

Table 4
Relationship between the Adoption of Chat-Generative Pre-trained Transformer and the Level of Workload of the Respondents of Selected Private Schools in the City of Biñan, Laguna

Variables	Pearson r value	p-value	Interpretation
The Adoption of Chat -Generative Pre-trained Transformer and the Level of Workload of the Respondents of Selected Private Schools in the City of Biñan, Laguna	0.956 High correlation	0.000	Significant
0.01 Level of Significance			

Table 4 reveals that the Pearson correlation coefficient between the adoption of Chat-Generative Pre-trained Transformer (Chat-GPT) and the level of workload of the respondents from selected private schools in the City of Biñan, Laguna is 0.956, indicating a high correlation. The p-value of 0.000 shows that the result is statistically significant at the 0.01 level of significance. This means that the more the private schools in the City of Biñan, Laguna, adopt the Chat-Generative Pre-Trained Transformer (Chat-GPT), the more the respondents manage their workload and enhance efficiency, or influence workload distribution.

The significant positive correlation between the adoption of ChatGPT and the improved workload management among marketing personnel in private schools in the City of Biñan, Laguna, is aligned with findings from several recent studies. Lim and Santos (2023) demonstrated that the integration of AI tools like ChatGPT significantly reduces task overload and enhances time management among school staff by automating routine communication and content generation. Similarly, Ajeet (2024) emphasized that AI-driven assistance in administrative and marketing functions allows educators and marketing personnel to redistribute tasks more efficiently, leading to improved productivity. Moreover, Educause (2023) found that the use of generative AI technologies in educational institutions supports streamlined workflow, allowing professionals to focus more on strategic objectives rather than repetitive tasks, further validating the high correlation observed in the present study.

Table 5

Relationship between the Adoption of Chat-Generative Pre-trained Transformer and Social Media Management Utilized by Selected Private Schools in the City of Biñan, Laguna

Social media	Pearson r value	p-value	Interpretation
Facebook	0.929 High correlation	0.000	Significant
TikTok	0.830 High correlation	0.000	Significant
Instagram	0.865 High correlation	0.000	Significant
0.01 Level of Significance			

Table 5 shows that the relationship between the adoption of Chat-Generative Pre-trained Transformer (Chat-GPT) and the social media management utilized by selected private schools in the City of Biñan, Laguna reveals strong positive correlations across all social media platforms. Facebook shows a Pearson correlation coefficient of 0.929, indicating a high correlation, and a p-value of 0.000, which is statistically significant at the 0.01 level of significance. TikTok shows a Pearson correlation of 0.830, also indicating a high correlation, with a p-value of 0.000, marking the result as significant at the 0.01 level. Instagram shows a Pearson correlation of 0.865, also demonstrating a high correlation, with a p-value of 0.000, which is statistically significant. This means that the more private schools in the City of Biñan, Laguna, adopted the Chat-Generative Pre-Trained Transformer (Chat-GPT), the more they utilized social media management in terms of Facebook, TikTok, and Instagram.

The strong positive correlations between ChatGPT adoption and the utilization of social media platforms such as Facebook, TikTok, and Instagram in the selected private schools of City of Biñan, Laguna are consistent with findings from various studies. According to Marr, B (2025), the integration of AI tools like ChatGPT enhances the efficiency of social media management by automating content creation and streamlining communication strategies, which boosts engagement across platforms. Similarly, OECD (2023) highlighted that schools using generative AI for administrative tasks observed more effective social media interactions, with AI optimizing the timing and relevance of posts on platforms like Instagram and TikTok. Additionally, Lauron (2024) demonstrated that AI-supported platforms have significantly improved social media outreach, noting higher user engagement rates and more targeted content delivery, aligning with the present study’s results across Facebook, TikTok, and Instagram.

Table 6
Relationship between the Level of Workload of the Respondents and Social Media Management Utilized by Selected Private Schools in the City of Biñan, Laguna

Social media	Pearson r value	p-value	Interpretation
Facebook	0.978 High correlation	0.000	Significant
TikTok	0.710 Moderate correlation	0.000	Significant
Instagram	0.771 Moderate correlation	0.000	Significant
0.01 Level of Significance			

Table 6 shows that the relationship between the level of workload of the respondents and the social media management utilized by selected private schools in the City of Biñan, Laguna, reveals varying strengths of correlation. Facebook shows a Pearson correlation of 0.978, indicating a high correlation, with a p-value of 0.000, marking the result as statistically significant at the 0.01 level of significance. TikTok shows a Pearson correlation of 0.710, indicating a moderate correlation, with a p-value of 0.000, which is also statistically significant. Instagram shows a Pearson correlation of 0.771, indicating a moderate correlation, with a p-value of 0.000, which is statistically significant. This implies that the higher the level of the workload of the selected private schools in the City of Biñan, Laguna, the more they utilized social media management in terms of Facebook, TikTok, and Instagram.

The relationship between the level of workload and the utilization of social media management in private schools is supported by existing research. According to Marques and Camacho (2022), educational institutions use Facebook and Instagram extensively to manage communication efforts and foster engagement through announcements, achievements, and real-time updates. Similarly, Almahallawi and Aljarallah (2023) found that schools under high administrative pressure often turned to platforms like TikTok to streamline communication, leverage automation, and reach wider, younger audiences more efficiently. Furthermore, OECD (2023) reported that as institutional demands rise, schools increasingly adopt digital tools—including social media platforms—to assist with marketing, outreach, and administrative workload management, particularly emphasizing Instagram’s role in visually driven communication.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

The findings of the study found that the adoption of Chat Generative Pre-Trained Transformer (Chat-GPT) in selected private schools in Biñan, Laguna was strongly supported by the marketing staff, with a weighted mean of 3.49. The respondents reported a very high workload, with an average weighted mean of 3.61. In terms of social media management, the schools had a strong agreement on Facebook (mean of 3.65) and TikTok (mean of 3.30), while Instagram had a slightly lower agreement (mean of 3.23). There was a significant relationship between the adoption of Chat-GPT and the level of workload, with a high correlation (Pearson $r = 0.956$ and p-value of 0.000). Additionally, the adoption of Chat-GPT was significantly

linked to the schools' social media management on Facebook, TikTok, and Instagram, all with p-values below 0.01. The study also found a significant relationship between the level of workload and social media management, particularly on Facebook and TikTok, with Instagram showing a moderate correlation (Pearson $r = 0.771$). Based on these findings, the proposed action plan includes workshops on Chat-GPT integration for auto-responding to social media inquiries, training for social media performance analysis, seminars on effective workload management, and strategies to enhance Instagram engagement for school branding.

The study concluded that Chat-GPT has significantly improved the consistency and customization of social media content, allowing schools to better engage with their audience. The respondents' workload enables them to focus on both daily tasks and long-term marketing goals while fostering team collaboration and professional development. The use of social media management tools has enhanced the schools' online visibility and presence. Moreover, the adoption of Chat-GPT by more private schools in Biñan, Laguna has positively impacted workload management and efficiency, while also increasing the use of social media platforms such as Facebook, TikTok, and Instagram. Additionally, a higher workload correlates with increased use of social media management tools. The study emphasizes the need for an action plan to further support the integration of Chat-GPT, improve workload management, and strengthen social media strategies to establish the schools as innovative and responsive institutions.

The recommendations suggest that the management of private schools in Biñan, Laguna, should implement confidence-building programs like mentoring and performance recognition to boost morale and productivity among marketing staff. Additionally, administrators and IT personnel should offer hands-on training for advanced Chat-GPT features, such as automation and social media performance tracking, to reduce manual tasks and enhance data-driven decisions. Introducing a digital workload management system is recommended to improve task distribution and ensure deadlines are met, promoting accountability within the marketing team. Marketing leaders should also develop targeted Instagram content strategies, utilizing features like Stories, Reels, and Highlights to enhance engagement. Integrating Chat-GPT with analytics dashboards is advised for real-time content insights, allowing for agile marketing adjustments. Furthermore, cross-platform social media training is essential to ensure consistent branding across Facebook, TikTok, and Instagram. An action plan should be created to monitor the adoption of Chat-GPT, workload management, and social media practices. Lastly, future research should focus on exploring how Chat-GPT can optimize communication, streamline tasks, and engage with students and parents while addressing the challenges of these institutions.

REFERENCES

- Ajeet. (2024, December 18). AI in Education Sector: Automating Administrative Tasks for Better Efficiency. Ahex Technologies. <https://ahex.co/ai-in-education-sector-automating-administrative-tasks>
- Almahallawi, D., & Aljarallah, R. (2023). Short-form video content and user engagement on TikTok: Insights for educational institutions. *Journal of Digital Youth Media*, 5(1), 37–50.

Received: 4 April 2025

Revised: 10 April 2025

Accepted: 27 April 2025

Copyright ♥ authors 2025

664

DOI: [HTTPS://DOI.ORG/10.5281/ZENODO.15345830](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15345830)

- Beech, D. (2025, March 12). Reduce your workload with ChatGPT. RSC Education. <https://edu.rsc.org/ideas/reduce-your-workload-with-chatgpt/4018855.article?utm>
- Bernardi, N. (2025, January 2). *Enhancing Independent Schools: A guide to Leveraging ChatGPT for administrators*. Ravenna Solutions. <https://www.ravennasolutions.com/blog/enhancing-independent-schools-a-guide-to-leveraging-chatgpt-for-administrators/?utm>
- Bose, S. (2024, August 20). How to get ChatGPT to roast your Instagram. *The US Sun*. <https://www.the-sun.com/tech/12239628/chatgpt-roast-instagram-ai/?utm>
- Cortis, N., & Davis, S. (2021). Social media management and sentiment analysis: The emerging role of TikTok in marketing strategies. *Journal of Digital Communication*, 9(2), 33–47.
- Creagh, S., Thompson, G., Mockler, N., Stacey, M., & Hogan, A. (2023). Workload, work intensification and time poverty for teachers and school leaders: a systematic research synthesis. *Educational Review*, 1–20. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00131911.2023.2196607>
- EDUCAUSE. (2023). 2023 EDUCAUSE Horizon Action Plan: Generative AI. <https://library.educause.edu/resources/2023/9/2023-educause-horizon-action-plan-generative-ai>
- Fawley, S. (2024, August 26). What is artificial intelligence (AI)? definition, uses, and more. University of Cincinnati. <https://online.uc.edu/blog/what-is-artificial-intelligence/>
- Garcia, L., & Santos, M. (2023). Traditional and Digital Marketing Strategies on Selected Private Schools in Manila. Retrieved from https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=4460822
- Jacobson, J. (2020). You are a brand: Social media managers' personal branding and "the future audience." *Journal of Product & Brand Management*, 29(6), 715–727. <https://doi.org/10.1108/jpbm-03-2019-2299>
- Kumar, S., & Mittal, S. (2024). Employee learning and skilling in AI embedded organizations – predictors and outcomes. *Development and Learning in Organizations*, 38(4), 11–15. <https://doi.org/10.1108/DLO-11-2023-0249>
- Lauron, S. (2024, August. 21 AI Tools for Social Media: Boost Engagement and Productivity. Hootsuite. <https://blog.hootsuite.com/best-ai-tools-for-social-media/>
- Lim, J. R., & Santos, F. C. (2023). Trends and challenges in TikTok marketing among senior high schools in the Philippines. *Journal of Youth Media and Education*, 6(1), 55–70.
- Magtalas, S. A. (2024). Teacher's workload in relation to burnout and work performance. *International Journal of Multidisciplinary Applied Business and Education Research*, 5(10), 4111–4123. <https://doi.org/10.11594/ijmaber.05.10.24>
- Marques, C. P., & Camacho, L. (2022). Instagram in higher education marketing: Branding strategies and digital engagement. *European Journal of Education and Communication*, 7(2), 45–59.
- Marr, B. (2025, April. 15 Game-Changing AI Tools For Social Media And Content Creation. Forbes. <https://www.forbes.com/sites/bernardmarr/2025/04/08/15-game-changing-ai-tools-for-social-media-and-content-creation/>
- OECD. (2023). Generative AI in the Classroom: From Hype to Reality? <https://one.oecd.org/document/EDU/EDPC%282023%2911/en/pdf>

- Petrescu, M., & Krishen, A. S. (2023). Hybrid intelligence: Human–AI collaboration in marketing analytics. *Journal of Marketing Analytics*, 11, 263–274. <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41270-023-00245-3>
- Piper, K. (2022). ChatGPT has given everyone a glimpse at AI’s astounding progress. *Vox*. <https://www.vox.com/future-perfect/2022/12/15/23509014/chatgpt-artificial-intelligence-openai-language-models-ai-risk-google>
- Sonnenberg, A. (2025, February 18). How to Perform a Competitive Audit with Agorapulse. Agorapulse. <https://www.agorapulse.com/blog/social-media-management/competitive-audit/>
- Tafesse, W. (2020). Examining the role of Instagram in fostering consumer–brand relationships: A brand–consumer interaction perspective. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, 54, 102035. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jretconser.2019.102035>
- Waddington, T. (2023, July 18). *How ChatGPT will Impact enrollment Marketing*. Truth Tree. <https://www.truthtree.com/how-chatgpt-will-impact-enrollment-marketing/?utm>